

Assessing job satisfaction and stress among pharmacists in Bulgaria: a cross-sectional study

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Abstract

Pharmacists are increasingly recognized as vital contributors to healthcare systems, with expanding clinical roles and responsibilities. This study aims to evaluate the well-being, job satisfaction, and stress levels among pharmacists in Bulgaria, a country where the pharmaceutical profession is undergoing transformation in alignment with European standards. A cross-sectional survey was conducted using a structured, self-administered 16-item questionnaire distributed online to licensed pharmacists across various practice settings. The survey collected demographic data and explored domains such as job satisfaction, work-related stress, salary perception, and work-life balance. A total of 401 pharmacists participated. Statistical analyses revealed a weak but significant negative correlation between job satisfaction and stress levels and a moderate negative correlation between stress and both work-life balance and salary satisfaction. No significant correlation was found between stress levels and either age or workplace setting. These findings suggest that systemic workplace factors, rather than demographic variables, are the primary drivers of stress among pharmacists. The study concludes that targeted strategies such as improving compensation, promoting job flexibility, and supporting work-life balance are crucial to enhancing pharmacists' well-being and mitigating burnout. These interventions are essential not only for workforce sustainability but also for maintaining high standards in pharmaceutical care and public health outcomes.

Keywords

pharmacists, job satisfaction, stress levels, burnout, community pharmacy

Introduction

The World Health Organization (WHO) has recognized pharmacists as the most accessible healthcare professionals (FIP/WHO guidelines 2011). Globally, the role of pharmacists has evolved, positioning them as healthcare providers with significant expertise in pharmacotherapy (Sanii et al. 2016). Traditionally, pharmacists were primarily responsible for the preparation, storage, distribution, and dispensing of medications, including ensuring

appropriate dosages and providing brief consultations (Harnett et al. 2023). However, this role has increasingly transitioned to a more clinical focus, with pharmacists now engaging in point-of-care testing and vaccination administration (Witry 2025). In emergency contexts, such as widespread outbreaks of infectious diseases, wars, or natural disasters, the importance of pharmacists' roles has intensified, leading to heightened stress levels and potential burnout (Ahmer et al. 2023). Sustained pressure can adversely affect their quality of life and contribute to dissat-

isfaction with their professional career (Dee et al. 2023). The pharmaceutical profession is classified as a regulated field in Bulgaria, with formal training programs designed to equip individuals with expertise in medication therapy management (Petkova and Atkinson 2017). Bulgarian pharmacists pursue professional careers across a variety of practice settings (Zaykova et al. 2022). In recent years, particularly following the COVID-19 pandemic, numerous studies have highlighted the heightened levels of burnout and stress experienced by healthcare professionals, including pharmacists (Johnston et al. 2021).

The evolution of the pharmaceutical profession has been shaped by advancements in healthcare, societal needs, and emerging scientific knowledge (Khakurel et al. 2019). Historically, pharmacists primarily focused on the preparation, dispensation, and management of medicines, ensuring correct dosages and offering brief consultations to patients (Higby and Urick 2021). Their expertise was primarily grounded in the technical aspects of pharmaceutical sciences. However, as healthcare systems have become increasingly complex, the role of pharmacists has expanded significantly (Dolovich et al. 2018). One key factor driving this evolution has been the growing emphasis on pharmacotherapy and the optimization of drug therapy outcomes (Tachkov et al. 2019). Pharmacists' expertise in the safe and effective use of medications has made them invaluable in the management of chronic diseases, medication therapy management (MTM), and patient counseling (Francis and Abraham 2014). They are now routinely involved in the clinical decision-making process, collaborating with other healthcare providers such as physicians, nurses, and other specialists to ensure that patients receive the most effective and appropriate treatment plans (Muscat et al. 2024). This transformation has also been facilitated by the increasing recognition of the pharmacist's role in preventative care (Abubakar and Sinclair 2020). Pharmacists have been increasingly involved in immunization programs, patient education on lifestyle changes, and the monitoring of patients' health metrics such as blood pressure, blood glucose, and cholesterol levels (Harpe 2024). These expanded responsibilities are often referred to as "clinical pharmacy," marking a shift from a purely technical function to a more patient-centered and healthcare-oriented role (Miozza et al. 2024). Technological advances have also played a significant role in shaping the modern pharmacist's role. The integration of electronic health records (EHRs) and pharmacy management systems has enabled pharmacists to work more effectively with other healthcare providers, ensuring that patient information is seamlessly shared and that drug interactions, allergies, and other critical information are easily accessible (Balogun et al. 2023). In addition, innovations in drug delivery systems, biotechnology, and personalized medicine have further elevated the pharmacist's position as a healthcare provider involved in cutting-edge treatments (Connelly 2024).

Despite these advancements, the evolving role of pharmacists has also presented challenges (Cherecheș et

al. 2024). The increased demand for their services, particularly in clinical settings and public health crises, has resulted in heightened stress levels and, in some cases, burnout (Austin and Gregory 2020). Pharmacists are now expected to balance their technical expertise with patient-facing responsibilities that can be emotionally taxing and physically demanding. As a result, many pharmacists face challenges related to work-life balance, job satisfaction, and mental health, which can have a negative impact on their quality of life (Soleimani et al. 2024).

The pharmaceutical profession in Bulgaria has undergone significant development in recent decades, driven by both national reforms and alignment with European Union (EU) standards (Petkova and Atkinson 2017). Pharmacists in Bulgaria are highly trained professionals, typically completing a five-year university degree in pharmacy followed by practical training (Ivanova et al. 2020). The profession is governed by the Bulgarian Pharmaceutical Union, which ensures that pharmacists adhere to ethical guidelines and maintain high standards of practice. In line with EU regulations, Bulgarian pharmacists are integral to the healthcare system, playing a crucial role in the dispensation and safe use of medications, patient counseling, and medication therapy management (Staynova et al. 2021). Over recent years, there has been a growing emphasis on the clinical role of pharmacists, with increasing involvement in preventive healthcare initiatives, chronic disease management, and health promotion activities. The evolving scope of pharmacy practice in Bulgaria mirrors global trends, with pharmacists becoming more active in multidisciplinary healthcare teams, particularly in primary care settings (Bogdanova et al. 2014). However, challenges such as the growing demand for their services, work-related stress, and the need for continued professional development in the face of rapid medical and technological advancements remain prevalent. Nonetheless, the pharmaceutical profession in Bulgaria is an essential component of the healthcare system, contributing significantly to public health and the effective use of medicinal therapies.

Materials and methods

Systematic review

A comprehensive literature search was performed across multiple electronic databases, including PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. The search was conducted using a combination of MeSH terms and keywords, including "pharmacist well-being," "professional satisfaction," "quality of life," "burnout," and "Bulgaria." Boolean operators (AND, OR) were used to refine the search results. No language restrictions were applied, and studies published from January 2000 to March 2025 were considered.

This study employed a cross-sectional survey design to assess pharmacists' well-being and professional satisfaction in Bulgaria. A self-administered questionnaire was developed to collect data on various aspects of job

satisfaction, work-related stress, and quality of life among practicing pharmacists.

Questionnaire development

A structured questionnaire consisting of 16 items was designed based on a review of existing literature on pharmacist well-being and burnout. The survey included both closed-end and Likert scale questions, covering the following domains:

1. Demographic information (age, gender, years of experience, workplace setting)
2. Job satisfaction (workload, professional recognition, career development opportunities)
3. Work-related stress and burnout (emotional exhaustion, workload perception, job demands)
4. Quality of life (work-life balance, mental and physical well-being)

To ensure content validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by four pharmacy professionals and four academic experts before distribution.

Data collection

The questionnaire was distributed online and made accessible through the official website and social media platforms of the Bulgarian Pharmaceutical Union. Participation was voluntary, and pharmacists were informed about the study's objectives before completing the survey. Responses were collected anonymously to encourage honest feedback.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The inclusion criteria were licensed pharmacists practicing in Bulgaria across community pharmacies, hospital pharmacies, industry, and academia. Exclusion criteria: pharmacy students, retired pharmacists, and individuals not actively engaged in pharmacy practice.

Ethical considerations

The study adhered to ethical guidelines for survey-based research. Informed consent was obtained electronically from all participants before they proceeded with the questionnaire. The anonymity and confidentiality of responses were maintained throughout the study.

Data analysis

Survey responses were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Frequency distributions and percentages were used to summarize categorical variables, while mean and standard deviation were calculated for continuous variables. Chi-square tests and t-tests were used to assess associations between demographic factors

and job satisfaction levels. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 401 pharmacists participated in the study. Of these, 218 were employed in community pharmacies, 20% worked in clinical research companies, 9% were engaged in academic roles, and 6% were employed in hospital pharmacies (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. What is your current occupation?

The analysis revealed several significant relationships between workplace stress and key professional factors among Bulgarian pharmacists (Table 1).

Table 1. Pharmacists' job satisfaction and well-being.

Category	Response	n (%)
Thinking about work after hours	Yes	245 (72.1%)
	No	156 (27.9%)
Perceived job difficulty	Considered "heavy"	212 (55.7%)
	Not considered "heavy"	189 (44.3%)
Fair compensation for work	Not at all	128 (29.9%)
	Not fully	160 (46.8%)
	Yes	113 (23.4%)
Job satisfaction	Satisfied	236 (67.7%)
	Not satisfied	165 (32.3%)
Time for hobbies and relaxation	Yes	147 (39.3%)
	Yes, but feeling exhausted	141 (37.3%)
	No	113 (23.4%)
Panic attacks in the past year	Yes	152 (25.9%)
	No	249 (74.1%)
Use of nervous system medication	Yes	152 (25.9%)
	No	249 (74.1%)
Self-perception as a positive person	Yes	269 (84.1%)
	No	132 (15.9%)
Self-identification as happy	Often yes	141 (45.3%)
	Yes	118 (33.8%)
Category	Response	n (%)
	Often no	86 (17.9%)
	No	56 (3.0%)
Stress levels at work (scale 1–5)	Mean score	3.56
	Standard deviation	1.06
	Most frequent ratings:	3 or 4 (moderate to high)
Would choose pharmacy again	Yes	218 (58.7%)
	No	183 (41.3%)

A negative correlation was found between job satisfaction and stress levels ($r = -0.185$, $p = 0.008$), indicating that pharmacists who reported lower job satisfaction experienced higher stress levels (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Stress levels and job satisfaction relation.

Similarly, work-life balance was negatively correlated with stress ($r = -0.411$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that pharmacists struggling to find time for hobbies and relaxation reported significantly higher stress (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Pharmacists work-life balance influenced by stress levels.

Regarding salary satisfaction, a moderate negative correlation with stress levels was observed ($r = -0.291$, $p = 0.0023$), demonstrating that pharmacists who perceived their salaries as fair reported lower stress. However, age did not show a significant correlation with stress ($r = 0.112$, $p = 0.114$), implying that stress levels remain relatively constant across different age groups.

Further, stress levels varied across different workplace settings, though an ANOVA test showed no statistically significant differences ($F = 1.619$, $p = 0.096$). This suggests

that while individual perceptions of stress may vary, the type of workplace itself does not have a strong influence on overall stress levels.

These findings highlight that workplace stress among Bulgarian pharmacists is primarily influenced by job satisfaction, work-life balance, and salary perception, rather than age or workplace setting. Addressing these factors through improved compensation, job flexibility, and work-life balance initiatives could help mitigate pharmacist burnout and improve overall well-being (Abubakar and Sinclair 2020).

There is a weak but statistically significant negative correlation between job satisfaction and stress levels ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that as workplace stress increases, job satisfaction tends to decrease. While the correlation is not very strong, it confirms that stress is a contributing factor to pharmacists' dissatisfaction. There is a moderate and statistically significant negative correlation between stress levels and work-life balance. This means that pharmacists who report higher stress levels are significantly less likely to have time for hobbies and relaxation. The strength of the correlation suggests that workplace stress has a meaningful impact on pharmacists' ability to maintain a healthy work-life balance. There is a very weak positive correlation between age and stress levels, but it is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). This suggests that age does not play a major role in determining workplace stress levels among Bulgarian pharmacists. There is a moderate negative correlation between stress levels and salary satisfaction. This means that pharmacists who feel fairly compensated tend to experience lower stress levels, while those who perceive their salary as unfair report higher stress. The correlation is statistically significant ($p < 0.01$), indicating a meaningful relationship between these factors.

Discussion

The study's findings clarify critical factors influencing the well-being of Bulgarian pharmacists, highlighting the interplay between job satisfaction, work-life balance, and perceived salary (Hanh et al. 2022; Abubakar and Sinclair 2020). While the role of pharmacists has evolved to encompass more clinical responsibilities (Witry 2025), this evolution has also introduced challenges, including heightened stress and burnout (Johnston et al. 2021). The negative correlation between job satisfaction and stress levels ($r = -0.185$, $p = 0.008$) underscores the importance of fostering a positive work environment.

Furthermore, the significant negative correlation between work-life balance and stress ($r = -0.411$, $p < 0.001$) emphasizes the need for interventions that promote a healthy equilibrium between professional and personal life. Pharmacists struggling to find time for hobbies and relaxation reported significantly higher stress, aligning with global concerns about pharmacist well-being [24]. The moderate negative correlation between salary satisfaction and stress levels ($r = -0.291$, $p = 0.0023$) suggests

that fair compensation plays a crucial role in mitigating stress (Tachkov et al. 2019; Abubakar and Sinclair 2020).

Interestingly, age did not significantly correlate with stress (Abubakar and Sinclair 2020), indicating that stress levels remain relatively constant across different age groups. This suggests that systemic factors, rather than individual characteristics, are the primary drivers of stress among Bulgarian pharmacists. Addressing these factors through improved compensation, job flexibility, and work-life balance initiatives could help mitigate pharmacist burnout and improve overall well-being (Muscat et al. 2024).

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the well-being of Bulgarian pharmacists, revealing significant associations between workplace stress and key professional factors. The findings underscore that job satisfaction, work-life balance, and perceived salary are critical determinants of stress levels among pharmacists (Abubakar and Sinclair 2020; Muscat et al. 2024). Unlike some assumptions, age and workplace setting did not strongly influence overall stress levels (Tachkov et al. 2014; Muscat et al. 2024), suggesting that systemic workplace factors are the primary drivers.

These results call for targeted interventions to mitigate pharmacist burnout and improve overall well-being. Healthcare administrators and policymakers should prioritize strategies that enhance job satisfaction, promote work-life balance, and ensure fair compensation (Muscat et al. 2024). Further research could explore specific interventions, such as flexible work arrangements, stress management programs, and enhanced professional development opportunities.

By addressing these key stressors, the pharmaceutical profession in Bulgaria can foster a more supportive and sustainable work environment. This, in turn, will en-

hances the quality of pharmaceutical care provided to the public, contributing to improved patient outcomes and a more resilient healthcare system.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Medical University of Plovdiv.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Abubakar A, Sinclair J (2020) The emerging role of community pharmacists in remote patient monitoring services. *Pharmacy* 8(3): e166. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmacy8030166>
- Ahmer Raza M, Aziz S, Noreen M, Masood Raza S (2021) Role of pharmacist in disaster management: A quantitative content analysis approach. *Innovations in Pharmacy* 12(4). <https://doi.org/10.24926/iip.v12i4.4359>
- Austin Z, Gregory P (2020) Resilience in the time of pandemic: The experience of community pharmacists during COVID-19. *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy* 17(1): 1867–1875. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sapharm.2020.05.027>
- Balogun NOD, Ayo-Farai NO, Ogundairo NO, Maduka NCP, Okongwu NCC, Babarinde NaO, Sodamade NOT (2023) Innovations in drug delivery systems: A review of the pharmacist's role in enhancing efficacy and patient compliance. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews* 20(3): 1268–1282. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.20.3.2587>
- Bogdanova L, Grigorov E, Belcheva V, Getov I (2014) Ad hoc study of the role of hospital pharmacists in clinical trials in Bulgaria. *Scripta Scientifica Pharmaceutica* 1(1): 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.14748/ssp.v1i1.600>
- Cherecheş MC, Finta H, Prisada RM, Rusu A (2024) Pharmacists' professional satisfaction and challenges: A netnographic analysis of reddit and facebook discussions. *Pharmacy* 12(5): e155. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmacy12050155>
- Connelly D (2024) Special report: the stressors burning out pharmacists. *The Pharmaceutical Journal* 313(7988): e313. <https://doi.org/10.1211/PJ.2024.1.324833>
- Dee J, Dhuhaibawi N, Hayden JC (2023) A systematic review and pooled prevalence of burnout in pharmacists. *International journal of clinical pharmacy* 45(5): 1027–1036. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11096-022-01520-6>

- Dolovich L, Austin Z, Waite N, Chang F, Farrell B, Grindrod K, Houle S, McCarthy L, MacCallum L, Sproule B (2018) Pharmacy in the 21st century: Enhancing the impact of the profession of pharmacy on people's lives in the context of health care trends, evidence and policies. *Canadian pharmacists journal* 152(1): 45–53. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1715163518815717>
- Francis J, Abraham S (2014) Clinical pharmacists: Bridging the gap between patients and physicians. *Saudi Pharmaceutical Journal* 22(6): 600–602. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsps.2014.02.011>
- Hanh J, Hazell P, Feijo I (2022) The pharmacist and pharmacotherapy. *Longer- Term Psychiatric Inpatient Care for Adolescents*, Palgrave Macmillan, Singapore, 283–294. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-1950-3_17
- Harnett JE, Desselte SP, Fernandes MB, Yao D, Modun D, Hallit S, Dabbous M, Abd Wahab MS, Cavaco AM, Magalhes M, Fall-er EM, Flores JM, San Gabriel JRD, Othman N, Anantachoti P, Sriboonruang T, Sriviriyanupap W, Alnezary F, Alahmadi Y, Fallatah SB, Fadil HA, Ung COL (2023) Defining and supporting a professional role for pharmacists associated with traditional and complementary medicines: a cross-country survey of pharmacists. *Frontiers in Pharmacology* 14: e1215475. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2023.1215475>
- Harpe SE (2024) Pharmacy in 2050: To succeed, we must adapt. *Journal of the American Pharmacists Association* 65(1): e102287. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.japh.2024.102287> [Epub 2024 Nov 12. PMID: 39536801]
- Higby GJ, Urick BY (2021) History of pharmacy. Remington: 3–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-820007-0.00001-5>
- Ivanova M, Todorova A, Georgieva L (2020) Burnout syndrome in bulgarian pharmacists – Pilot Study. *Proceedings of CBU in Medicine and Pharmacy* 1: 36–40. <https://doi.org/10.12955/pmp.v1.95>
- Johnston K, O'Reilly CL, Scholz B, Georgousopoulou EN, Mitchell I (2021) Burnout and the challenges facing pharmacists during COVID-19: results of a national survey. *International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy* 43(3): 716–725. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11096-021-01268-5>
- Khakurel B, Shrestha R, Joshi S, Thomas D (2019) Evolution of the pharmacy profession and public health. *Clinical Pharmacy Education, Practice and Research*: 13–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-814276-9.00002-7>
- Miozza M, Brunetta F, Appio FP (2024) Digital transformation of the pharmaceutical industry: A future research agenda for management studies. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 207: e123580. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2024.123580>
- Muscat NA, Sinclair P, Zapata T, Connolly D, Pinto GS, Kniazkov S (2024) Embracing pharmacists' roles in health-care delivery. *The Lancet Regional Health – Europe* 46: e101088. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanepe.2024.101088>
- Petkova V, Atkinson J (2017) Pharmacy practice and education in Bulgaria. *Pharmacy* 5(3): e35. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmacy5030035>
- Sanii Y, Torkamandi H, Gholami K, Hadavand N, Javadi M (2016) Role of pharmacist counseling in pharmacotherapy quality improvement. *Journal of research in pharmacy practice* 5(2): 132–137. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2279-042X.179580>
- Soleimani E, Tahmasebi R, Daneshmandi H, Salimi SH, Aliasghari F (2024) Work-life balance and health among pharmacists: Physical activity, sleep quality, and general health. *BMC Health Services Research* 24(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-024-11701-w>
- Staynova R, Gvozdeva Y, Peikova L, Mihaylova A (2021) Bulgarian community pharmacists' attitudes and barriers towards pharmaceutical care provision for pregnant women. *Pharmacia* 68(3): 511–516. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.68.e68651>
- Tachkov K, Mitov K, Mitkova Z, Kamusheva M, Dimitrova M, Petkova V, Savova A, Doneva M, Tcarukciev D, Valov V, Angelova G, Manova MM, Petrova G (2019) Improved quality of diabetes control reduces complication costs in Bulgaria. *Biotechnology & Biotechnological Equipment* 33(1): 814–820. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13102818.2019.1604160>
- Witry M (2025) The role of community pharmacists in point-of-care testing and treatment for influenza and Group A Streptococcus -a narrative review using Ecological Systems Theory. *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sapharm.2025.01.007>
- World Health Organization & International Pharmaceutical Federation (2011) Annex 8: Joint FIP/WHO guidelines on good pharmacy practice – standards for quality of pharmacy services (WHO Tech. Rep. Ser. No. 961, Annex 8). <https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/...pdf>
- Zaykova H, Zaykov H, Nikolova S, Serbezova A (2022) Influences when deciding to study pharmacy in Bulgaria: A Survey amongst pharmacists and pharmacy students. *Acta Scientific Pharmaceutical Sciences* 6(9): 51–59. <https://doi.org/10.31080/ASPS.2022.06.0916>